

Tako-Tsubo Cardiomyopathy Following Surgery: A Two-Case Reports

Amine Bachar, Mahassine Rayadi ✉, Kamal Benzidane, Zakaria Essaidi,
Taoufik El Abbassi, Fatima Zahra Bensardi

Department of General Surgery, Ibn Rochd Hospital, Hassan II University,
Faculty of Medicine and Pharmacy, Tarik Ibn Ziad Street, Morocco

Abstract

Stress cardiomyopathy, also known as Tako-Tsubo syndrome, is a rare and transient condition that mimics acute myocardial infarction in the absence of significant coronary artery lesions. It remains a diagnosis of exclusion. It occurs predominantly in postmenopausal women and can be triggered by intense emotional or physical stress. In a surgical context, this condition may be underrecognized and mistaken for other cardiovascular emergencies. Through two clinical cases, this article discusses the clinical, paraclinical, pathophysiological, and therapeutic features of Tako-Tsubo syndrome, with a focus on its differential diagnosis and prognosis.

More Information

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Introduction

First described in Japan in 1990, Tako-Tsubo cardiomyopathy (also known as broken heart syndrome) is a transient and reversible left ventricular dysfunction triggered by acute stress. It owes its name to the characteristic shape of the left ventricle during systole, which resembles a traditional Japanese octopus trap ("tako-tsubo") [1]. Its prevalence is estimated to be between 1.7% and 2.2% of acute coronary syndromes (ACS), with a marked female predominance (a female-to-male ratio of 9:1) [2], mainly in postmenopausal women. The triggering

factors vary and include emotional stress, psychological shock, intense pain, or physical aggression, such as major surgery [3,4].

Observation

Case 1

A 70-year-old female patient with a history of small bowel resection for mesenteric infarction presented 18 months later with an uncomplicated incisional hernia. Surgical repair was performed using a polypropylene mesh placed in the pre-fascial and retro-muscular planes.

Figure 1: Sinus Tachycardia with Non-Specific Repolarization Abnormalities

On postoperative day 3, the patient suddenly developed polypnea (27 breaths/min), tachycardia (120 bpm), hypotension (100/60 mmHg), and profuse sweating, without typical chest pain. Electrocardiography revealed sinus tachycardia with non-specific repolarization abnormalities.

Laboratory tests showed elevated troponin levels (105 ng/L) and D-dimers (1740 ng/mL). A thoracic CT angiogram ruled out pulmonary embolism. Echocardiography demonstrated mid-apical hypokinesia of the left ventricle, and coronary angiography was normal, ruling out an acute coronary syndrome (ACS). The diagnosis of Tako-Tsubo cardiomyopathy was made.

The clinical course was favorable under medical treatment, including beta-blockers and ACE inhibitors.

Case 2

A 48-year-old woman, with a history of type 1 diabetes, was treated for acute cholangitis on a tumor of the pancreatic head and underwent a biliodigestive bypass. On postoperative day 4, she developed a sudden clinical deterioration characterized by fever (39.5°C), polypnea (30 breaths/min), tachycardia (130 bpm), and oxygen desaturation (92%).

Laboratory tests revealed elevated troponin levels (4677 ng/L) and D-dimers (1890 ng/mL). A thoracic CT angiogram suggested a distal pulmonary embolism with bilateral pleural effusion. Acute cardiorespiratory failure was suspected based on ECG findings and echocardiography, which showed sinus tachycardia, apical hypokinesia, and a pericardial effusion.

Despite intensive care management, the patient passed away. In the absence of any other identifiable cause, the diagnosis of Tako-Tsubo syndrome was considered.

Figure 2: Sinus Tachycardia with Apical Hypokinesia

Discussion

Tako-Tsubo syndrome, also known as stress cardiomyopathy, is characterized by a unique pathophysiological mechanism. It typically occurs following intense physical or emotional stress, triggering a massive release of catecholamines. This hyperadrenergic state leads to direct myocardial toxicity, microvascular coronary vasoconstriction, and transient myocardial dysfunction, particularly affecting the apical and mid-ventricular regions of the left ventricle [5].

Several hypotheses have been proposed regarding the pathogenesis of this cardiomyopathy. The most widely accepted suggests an exaggerated stress response, with excessive stimulation of β -adrenergic receptors, resulting in reduced coronary perfusion and regional myocardial dysfunction. The regional distribution of β -adrenergic receptors within the left ventricle may explain the predominance of apical involvement [6].

Epidemiologically, studies report that nearly 90% of cases affect postmenopausal women. The absence of estrogen-mediated hormonal protection may render the myocardium more vulnerable to the deleterious effects of catecholamines. In postoperative settings, as illustrated in the presented cases, factors such as surgical stress, hypovolemia, acute pain, and

electrolyte imbalances may contribute to the onset of Tako-Tsubo syndrome [7].

Clinically, the syndrome often mimics acute coronary syndrome (ACS). However, coronary angiography helps rule out ACS by revealing no significant coronary stenosis. Echocardiography is a key diagnostic tool, typically showing akinesia or dyskinesia of the mid-apical segments, with compensatory basal hyperkinesia, producing the characteristic appearance of apical ballooning.

Prognosis is generally favorable, with left ventricular function recovering within a few days to weeks. Nonetheless, complications such as acute pulmonary edema, cardiogenic shock, ventricular arrhythmias, or intraventricular thrombus formation may worsen the clinical course. Therefore, close monitoring in an intensive care setting is essential during the acute phase [8].

There is no standardized treatment protocol to date. Current management is largely symptomatic, often modeled on therapies used for acute heart failure. These include beta-blockers to reduce sympathetic activity, ACE inhibitors or ARBs to prevent remodeling, and diuretics as needed. Anxiolytics or antidepressants may also be considered when emotional stress is identified as a trigger [8].

Conclusion

Postoperative Tako-Tsubo syndrome is a rare but serious complication that should be considered in any case of cardiocirculatory decompensation without significant coronary lesions. It remains a diagnosis of exclusion. Diagnosis relies on cardiac imaging and coronary angiography. Improved recognition of this condition allows for appropriate management, avoiding unnecessary treatments and improving prognosis. Heightened vigilance is warranted in postmenopausal women undergoing surgery in the context of major physical stress.

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